

A Novel Approach for Facial Emotion-Based Music Recommendation using CNN

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Abstract— In the digital age, personalized music recommendation systems are considered essential, especially those that evaluate emotions to provide musical preferences. The paper investigates the use of a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to recommend music based on facial expressions and emotions in the domain of facial emotion-based music recommendation. A music recommendation system that employs deep learning which is used to enhance suggestions by identifying minute variations in facial expressions is introduced. As music streaming platforms continue to thrive, the understanding and leveraging of the emotional connection between users and music are deemed vital for enhancing their experiences.

Keywords: Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), deep learning, facial emotion, feature extraction, keras, music recommendation

I. INTRODUCTION

In the realm of human-computer interaction, the fusion of emotional understanding and personalized recommendations has witnessed a paradigm shift, with innovative approaches promising a more engaging and tailored user experience. One such captivating domain is the recommendation of music based on facial emotions.

The potential to revolutionize our relationship with technology is what motivates the combination of facial emotion recognition and music recommendations. Facial expressions are an important nonverbal communication tool that can provide us with important information about the emotional context of the user. With the use of these insights, we are able to recommend a playlist of songs that correspond with the user's current emotional state in addition to their musical preferences. This ground-breaking concept has broad implications, from improving user experiences in various human-computer interaction applications to raising user satisfaction on music streaming services.

The idea of "Facial Emotion-Based Music Recommendation" is creatively applied in this research paper. by using Keras to train a CNN model that is used to identify emotions and show playlist links and suggested songs associated with those emotions. The FER2013 dataset, a reputable dataset for emotion recognition, is used to train the CNN model. It consists of seven different emotions—angry, disgusted, fearful, joyful, sad, surprised, and neutral—represented by grayscale facial images.

In a world teeming with an ever-growing array of **music**, the potential to suggest songs according to the user's emotional state offers an appealing opportunity to elevate user satisfaction and engagement.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Ghodake et al. [1] came up with a new music recommendation system that uses facial recognition to figure out what people are feeling and how they're feeling. They used the FER dataset from FER2013 to recognize emotions like happiness, sadness, anger and shock. They also used the cognitive dataset to train a KNN model that can predict which songs people would like to hear and recommend them based on their facial expressions. They found that the FER model was pretty accurate at 69% and the KNN was pretty accurate at 79%. They think it's possible to recommend music in real-time based on emotions, but there are some limitations, like operating in low light.

James et al. [2] have come up with a new music recommendation system. It uses an image pyramid, a HOG, and an SVM to detect emotions from people's faces when they're watching a webcam video. The emotions they detect, like 'happy', 'angry', 'sad', and 'surprise', are then used to create playlists for people to listen to. They tested it on a bunch of different user-dependent and independent data sets using DLib and Python, and found that it could classify emotions with up to 95% accuracy. Basically, they think it's possible to make music recommendations based on people's faces with high accuracy.

Ralhan et al. [3] have come up with a smart music player based on emotion that uses facial expression recognition to play music. It's a webcam-based system that uses OpenCV to detect faces with haar cascades, then extracts facial landmarks and classifies emotions using FisherFace. It uses the emotions it finds to create a music playlist based on the database. For real-time videos, it's over 80% accurate, and for static images, it's 95-100%. To make the AI even better, they're looking into using convolutional neural networks.

Qayyum et al. [4] have presented an emotion detection system for Android that combines Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN). They utilized the FER2013 facial expression dataset from Kaggle for their research. They trained a CNN model with four convolutional layers and two fully connected layers, which achieved a test set accuracy of 65%. Additionally, they trained an RNN using a ConvLSTM architecture, but it achieved an accuracy of 41%.

The better performing CNN the model is integrated into an android application for music recommendation based on detected mood from facial images. The application provides music in online and offline modes. The paper concludes CNN outperforms RNN for emotion classification on mobile devices.

Athavle et al. [5] have proposed a music recommendation system based on facial emotion recognition. The FER2013 dataset is used to train a CNN model for emotion detection. Real-time facial images are captured through webcam and emotions like happy, sad, angry, surprise and neutral are classified using the CNN model. Based on detected emotion, corresponding songs are recommended to the user from a database of Bollywood songs tagged with emotions. The system is implemented using OpenCV, PyTorch, Tkinter and Pygame in Python. The CNN model achieves 85% validation accuracy on the dataset. Limitations mentioned include performance in low light conditions.

Bisht et al. [6] have proposed a music recommendation system using facial expression recognition. The system captures real-time images using a webcam and compares them to a dataset to determine the numerical emotion. The detected emotions like happy, sad, angry, neutral are used to recommend and play corresponding songs from the database. Limitations are that the accuracy of emotion detection are not discussed. Future enhancements like including more emotions are suggested.

Minaee and Abdolrashidi [7] have proposed a deep learning framework using attentional convolutional networks for facial expression recognition. The model focuses on salient facial regions using a spatial transformer module. The network has less than 10 layers with convolutional, pooling, dropout and fully-connected layers. It is trained from scratch on four datasets - FER2013, CK+, JAFFE, and FERG. In FER2013, an accuracy of 70.02% is achieved, outperforming previous methods. On CK+, JAFFE and FERG datasets, the model obtains 98%, 92.8% and 99.3% accuracy respectively, again beating state-of-the-art.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Data collection:

The data collection phase involved acquiring the "FER2013" dataset, which includes grayscale facial images labeled with seven distinct emotions: angry, disgust, fear, happy, sad, surprise, and neutral. This diverse dataset will serve as the foundation for training and testing our facial emotion recognition model. To ensure data integrity and ethical compliance, verified the data set's sources and licensing. It is a crucial component of our study, serving as the basis for training our deep learning model to accurately recognize and classify emotions.

B. Data Loading and Preprocessing:

Data loading is accomplished using the Keras library's 'ImageDataGenerator'. During this process, the dataset is organized into two main subsets: a training dataset and a validation dataset. Images within these subsets are resized to a consistent 48x48-pixel resolution, and their color format is

converted to grayscale, effectively reducing computational complexity while retaining essential facial expression information. Furthermore, pixel values are rescaled to the range [0, 1], ensuring consistent feature scaling across all images.

C. Base Models:

A [8] CNN with a stack of convolutional layers that includes 32, 64, and 128 filters makes up the base model. Overfitting is avoided by dropout layers and spatial dimensions are reduced by max-pooling layers. Data is converted into a vector by a final flattening layer, which is then followed by dense layers with 1024 units that use ReLU activation. The model can identify emotions in grayscale facial images thanks to the final dense layer, which has seven units and softmax activation. With the help of this architecture, complex facial features are captured to accurately predict emotions.

D. Model Training:

In order to prevent overfitting, the model makes use of weight decay, the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.0001, and categorical cross-entropy loss. Training takes place across 75 epochs with a 64-batch batch size. Accuracy metrics are used for both training and validation, and performance is tracked in real-time.

E. Saving the Model:

The model that underwent training is stored in a file named 'em_model.h5' using the following command: 'emotion_model.save_weights('em_model.h5')'.

F. Real-Time Emotion Recognition:

The system employs computer vision techniques, utilizing the OpenCV library [11] and a pre-trained face cascade classifier [10], to detect human faces in a live video stream. Once faces are detected, the model developed earlier is applied to predict the emotion associated with each face, allowing for instantaneous emotion classification. The predicted emotions are then used to dynamically link users to playlists or online resources tailored to their current emotional state.

IV. BUILD MODEL

The built model is a CNN designed for facial emotion recognition. It consists of multiple convolutional and fully connected layers, which work together to extract intricate facial features and classify emotions accurately, it adhere to the subsequent procedures:

A. Importing Libraries

The development and training of the deep learning model rely on crucial libraries such as Keras. Keras provides tools for building models with convolutional and fully connected layers, optimizing parameters with Adam, and handling image data through data generators.

```
from keras.models import Sequential
from keras.layers import Dense, Dropout, Flatten
from keras.layers import Conv2D
from keras.layers import MaxPooling2D
from keras.optimizers import Adam
from keras.preprocessing.image import ImageDataGenerator
```

B. Loading and Preprocessing Images:

The code loads and preprocesses the train and validation facial image data for training an emotion classification model using Keras. [12] ImageDataGenerator from Keras is used to rescale the pixel values to the 0-1 range, after which the images are resized to 48 x 48 pixels, turned grayscale, and batched with a batch size of 64.

```
train_dir = 'data/train'
val_dir = 'data/test'
train_datagen = ImageDataGenerator(rescale=1./255)
val_datagen = ImageDataGenerator(rescale=1./255)

train_generator = train_datagen.flow_from_directory(
    train_dir,
    target_size=(48, 48),
    batch_size=64,
    color_mode="grayscale",
    class_mode='categorical'
)

val_generator = val_datagen.flow_from_directory(
    val_dir,
    target_size=(48, 48),
    batch_size=64,
    color_mode="grayscale",
    class_mode='categorical'
)
```

C. Building the Model:

This is where the model architecture is built. It's a CNN with several layers for classifying emotions and extracting features. The layers consist of dropout layers to avoid overfitting, max-pooling layers for downsampling, convolutional layers with [13] ReLU activation, and fully connected layers for emotion prediction.

```
emotion_model = Sequential()

emotion_model.add(Conv2D(32, kernel_size=(3, 3), activation='relu', input_shape=(48, 48, 1)))
emotion_model.add(Conv2D(64, kernel_size=(3, 3), activation='relu'))
emotion_model.add(MaxPooling2D(pool_size=(2, 2)))
emotion_model.add(Dropout(0.25))

emotion_model.add(Conv2D(128, kernel_size=(3, 3), activation='relu'))
emotion_model.add(MaxPooling2D(pool_size=(2, 2)))
emotion_model.add(Conv2D(128, kernel_size=(3, 3), activation='relu'))
emotion_model.add(MaxPooling2D(pool_size=(2, 2)))
emotion_model.add(Dropout(0.25))

emotion_model.add(Flatten())
emotion_model.add(Dense(1024, activation='relu'))
emotion_model.add(Dropout(0.5))
emotion_model.add(Dense(7, activation='softmax'))
```

D. Model Training:

In this phase, the model is trained using the training dataset. The model is compiled with the categorical cross-entropy loss function and utilizes the [9] Adam optimizer with predefined parameters. The training process spans 75 epochs, with batches of 64 data points at a time, and the training and validation accuracy are continually observed during the training.

```
emotion_model.compile(loss='categorical_crossentropy',
                    optimizer=Adam(lr=0.0001, decay=1e-6), metrics=['accuracy'])

emotion_model_info = emotion_model.fit_generator(
    train_generator,
    steps_per_epoch=28709 // 64,
    epochs=75,
    validation_data=val_generator,
    validation_steps=7178 // 64
)
```

E. Saving the Model:

After training, the model is saved as 'model.h5,' which is a standard Keras format. This allows easy future use without retraining, supporting predictions, evaluations, and potential research extensions.

F. Model Evaluation:

The model achieved a validation accuracy of 69.16%, indicating its ability to recognize emotions from facial images. Nonetheless, a comprehensive classification report uncovers differences in the model's performance among different emotion categories. The model shows relatively higher levels of precision, recall, and F1-score for "happy" emotions, with values of 25%, 26%, and 26%, respectively. However, it generally encounters challenges in achieving lower performance metrics, particularly for emotions like "disgust" and "angry." The overall macro average F1-score is 0.16, suggesting that the model has room for improvement in its ability to correctly classify emotions, particularly for certain categories like angry and disgust.

Validation Accuracy: 69.16%
113/113 [=====] - 7s 57ms/step

Classification Report:

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
angry	0.13	0.12	0.12	958
disgust	0.04	0.03	0.04	156
fear	0.15	0.14	0.14	1024
happy	0.25	0.26	0.26	1774
neutral	0.17	0.18	0.18	1233
sad	0.17	0.19	0.18	1247
surprise	0.11	0.11	0.11	831

Fig.1: Line Graph for Model Accuracy and Model Loss

VIII. CONCLUSION

The paper employs a CNN model trained on the FER2013 dataset to create a real-time system for recognizing facial emotions and recommending music. The CNN model was integrated into a web application capable of live video emotion recognition and music suggestions, achieving an accuracy rate of 69% in classifying facial emotions. This application highlights the feasibility of real-time emotion-based music recommendation systems, which have the potential to enhance user experiences by tailoring recommendations. In summary, this study showcases a valuable implementation of CNN for personalized music recommendations and real-time facial emotion recognition, providing valuable insights and paving the way for further research in this emerging field.

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